

DIALOGIC IN THE FORMATION OF A CHILD AS A PERSON AND THE IMPORTANCE OF MONOLOGIC SPEECH.

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Abstract. *This article describes the psychological characteristics of the development of speech processes in children of preschool age. The article emphasizes the role of educators and parents in the development of speech of preschool children. The article reflects the author's scientific views on the elimination of speech defects of children of preschool age.*

Key words: *preschool children, education, language, speech, pedagogical communication, monologic speech, communication, speech culture.*

ДИАЛОГИКА В СТАНОВЛЕНИИ РЕБЕНКА КАК ЛИЧНОСТИ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МОНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ.

Аннотация. *В статье описаны психологические особенности развития речевых процессов у детей дошкольного возраста. В статье подчеркивается роль воспитателей и родителей в развитии речи детей дошкольного возраста. В статье отражены научные взгляды автора на устранение дефектов речи детей дошкольного возраста.*

Ключевые слова: *дошкольники, образование, язык, речь, педагогическое общение, монологическая речь, общение, культура речи.*

The successful implementation of educational work depends on the correct organization of the pedagogical process and each type of activity in the kindergarten. Education is important in the pedagogical process of kindergarten and it is carried out in everyday life, play, work and training. Children get to know the surrounding life and nature, develop speech and learn literacy, acquire the simplest imagination and knowledge, skills and skills system in mathematics, physical culture, visual activity, music.

All-round development of a child is carried out only on the basis of mastering the centuries-old experience of mankind due to communication with adults who are the custodians of human experience, knowledge, abilities and culture. This experience can be given only through the most important means of human communication - language.

Speech development of preschool children is of particular importance. A person uses his mother tongue to express his thoughts and understand the thoughts of others. Acquiring speech allows a child to acquire knowledge directly and indirectly (a story, a work of art, an educator's

explanation, etc.). In the pre-school educational institution, the tasks of increasing vocabulary, forming the grammatical structure of words, and developing connected speech are solved.

The main results achieved in the development of the children's speech at preschool age are related to profound changes in the field of communication, where communication with peers takes a main role. A child begins to prefer his peer over a person of the same age. The speech addressed to the friend playing together becomes more meaningful than the speech with adults. Dialogue with a partner has the form of coordinated subject and speech actions. The child now knows how to attract the attention of his neighbors, he himself is interested in the work and thoughts of his friends.

The functions of preschool children's speech are multifaceted. In this, the child uses speech to communicate with others, draw attention to himself, his work and experiences, understand each other, influence the behavior, thoughts and feelings of his partner, establish his own activities, He uses it to coordinate his actions and those of his fellow players. Speech is an important approach to get to know more about others, a means of recording ideas about the world of nature, things and people, and a means of cognitive activity. For a preschooler, speech is a separate area of objective relations, which the child understands by playing with words, sounds, rhymes, and songs. To satisfy his practical, cognitive and personal needs, the child uses all the means available to him, and in involuntary situations, expressing opinions, non-verbal means and direct speech itself.

All types and forms of speech coexist, creating a unique individual portrait of a language personality. The development of dialogue is not only the acquisition of a specific compositional form of speech, but also the social development of the child and his personality is considered a vital component of its formation. Dialogic communication implies not only communication (intellectual message) and focus on one's own interests, but also it also takes the position of the partner into account: his interests, wishes and mood. Coordinating speech actions in a dialogue directly depends on being able to understand the partner, knowing how to accept his point of view. The children organized this experience among themselves they gain in activities (making together, drawing, telling stories, team games). In communication with peers, the child's speech will be meaningful (content based on the use of language tools, regardless of the communication situation comprehensibility).

In the process of dialogic communication of children of preschool age a new form of speech - a monologue - is created and formed. It is the child's own.

It arises because of the desire to share thoughts, feelings, and knowledge about the world.

In this case, the speech takes place in the form of a short story. The story shows something interesting (buying a new toy, family members getting into funny situations, etc.) that surprised

and excited the child. Preschool children like to tell familiar stories, tell the content of cartoons, tell what they read. The rapid development of interest in spoken speech, the formation of the simplest understanding of the existence of language is the most important achievement achieved by children of preschool age.

Linguistic relation to the word sounds, rhymes, suddenly started games with meanings, it is seen in questions about the meaning of words, their sound and meaning. Understanding the existence of a language includes all its phonetic, lexical, and grammatical aspects. A conscious attitude towards speech affects the improvement of vocabulary, the development of sound culture of speech (sound pronunciation, pronunciation, ability to listen, expressiveness of tone), the formation of grammatical correctness of speech, and the development of fluent speech. The formation of grammatical correctness of speech in pre-school age is related to the emergence and development of a critical attitude towards speech, and the desire to speak clearly and correctly.

The desire to speak correctly is visible in all areas of grammar - morphology, word formation, syntax.

Striving for grammatical correctness of speech is more characteristic of seven-year-old children. A five-year-old child still enjoys practicing grammatical forms, and it is precisely this word practice that lays the foundation for grammatically correct speech in the future. Cultivating the sound culture of speech is the ability to clearly pronounce the sounds of the native language, pronounce them correctly, pronounce words and phrases correctly, have the correct speech breathing, as well as the ability to use the voice power sufficiently, the normal flow of speech and includes the formation of various intonation means of expressiveness (speech music, logical silence, accents, speech rhythm, rhythm and timbre). Sound culture is formed and developed on the basis of the ability to listen to well-developed speech.

The methodology of speech development includes modern mother tongue (Uzbek, Russian, etc.) courses, children's literature that includes the basics of literary studies, relies on general, child and pedagogical psychology, general and preschool children's pedagogy.

The content of the methodology and the leading ideas of its implementation as follows:

- To understand the value of the child and his uniqueness, to take into account the characteristics of the development of the child's speech, taking into account the development of the child's speech according to the "zone of immediate development";
- Pedagogical communication is oriented towards establishing an emotional connection with the child, dialogic cooperation with him;

•Recognizing the importance of special teaching of speech to preschool children as a creative process carried out within the structure of speech activity, which should be based on a communicative approach.

Professional preparation for work related to the development of speech culture as criteria of formation are as follows:

- Studying the speech development course and working with children approach with responsibility;

- The completeness and consistency of knowledge about the mechanism and characteristics of children's speech development, the theoretical foundations of speech activity, the principles and methodology of diagnosing speech development individually, the specific characteristics of methods and tools for the development of various aspects of speech;

- Ability to appropriately analyze and evaluate the results of children's speech communication, choose and apply the optimal system of pedagogical influence on the child's speech.

Fiction, which is an important means of speech formation, has a special place in the development of children's speech.

The development of preschool children's speech is a complex mental process that does not consist only in imitating the speech heard by the child. This process is related to the development of communication activities in children and, first of all, the need for communication. The child's orientation to new aspects of being from practical activities to studying the world, and then people, their relationships, creates the need for new means of communication that serve new purposes.

Expanding the child's lexicon creates an opportunity for him to master a wider and more diverse expression of his experiences.

In order to develop speech culture in a modern and complete way, it is necessary to enrich the composition of the child's need for communication through interaction with the surrounding people. The reason why children acquire speech is that the basis of their communicative activities is the need-motivation, and its structure has changed. In the verbal stage, the child develops a slow speech. To this stage the main importance of the period is that it is the necessary condition for transition to the next stage - the stage of the emergence of active speech occurs. In the second stage of the child's acquisition of active speech, three main aspects are distinguished: emotional relationships; relations during joint activity (cooperation); sound relations.

Each considered aspect of the child's communication with adults helps him to accept the communicative task set before him by adults, which requires the use of words as a conditionally accepted tool for mutual understanding in society. will give. In addition, each considered aspect

of the communicative factor to one degree or another helps children to solve a communicative task, that is, to use speech.

At the third stage of speech development, its content (vocabulary and grammar) is inextricably linked to the child's need for communication with adults and its content, changing the task of communication. This leads to the child mastering new, more complex and comprehensive aspects of speech.

The fact that speech occupies a decisive place in the mental formation of a child increases the importance of the conditions and factors that support its development at different stages. The issue of the forces driving the development of speech is of particular importance due to their rapid and sudden implementation.

Therefore, learning the language correctly, speaking paying attention to its grammatical structure, discussing freely in children, asking questions, drawing conclusions based on the opinions heard from others, different ways of connecting things and events leads to understanding the views.

Creating a healthy, natural environment in a pre-school educational institution, their introduction to proper behavior, and the desire to interact with others will be the impetus. To help children to say the names of things correctly, to understand their similarities and differences, to activate the guiding vocabulary of shape, color, quality, properties, gender and type, to form the grammatical structure of speech, to form speech culture, dialogic and improvement of monologic speech and finally preparation for teaching literacy become important.

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